

Implementation of Clinical Practice Guidelines for Hepatitis C Infection

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Background

- Hepatitis C Virus (HCV) is a chronic liver infection that affects 3-5 million Americans annually
- HCV tripled between 2011-2016 with increase in IV drug use
- Timely screening and treatment can prevent disease transmissions, end-stage liver disease, and liver cancer

Purpose

- To develop, implement and evaluate EBP guidelines for screening and treatment of patients- at risk for or with HCV infection at GI clinic

Methods

- Setting: Outpatient GI clinic
- Participants: MD, nurse practitioner (TL), receptionist, MAs, IT specialists, financial services employees
- Data Collection: 12 weeks
- Outcome Measures: Total # of patients with HCV risk factors/total # of patients getting screened for HCV
- Analysis/Evaluation: QI Macros, Control charts

Theoretical Framework

Control Charts

Figure 1. Control chart (p chart) demonstrating special cause variations in week 7 after initiation of PDSA cycles #2 which included bi-weekly meetings with staff. Average compliance for identifying risk factors increased from 49% to 71%

Figure 2. Control chart (p chart) demonstrating special cause variations in week 7 and week 8 (PDSA cycles 2 and 3). Average compliance for obtaining blood test for eligible patients increased from 65% to 88%

Findings

- HCV screening rates increased from 50% to 71% at the end of the project
- Total patients screened for positive or at risk for HCV N= 1178
- Total patients with HCV risk factors N= 701
- Total HCV screening lab tests provided to patients with risk factors 74.9% (n= 525)
- Total number of patients' diagnostic HCV results received back 49% (n= 257)
- Currently 27 HCV positive patients monitored with new standardized protocol

Discussion

- Timely HCV screening and treatment can reduce disease mortality and morbidity rates
- Barriers: HCV awareness, time, insurance coverage, societal stigma, patients' refusal to screening, absence of lab within clinic, presence of family members
- Team involvement essential for success of such QI project

Limitations

- Number of providers and staff
- Lack of HCV awareness
- Barriers faced by providers and patients
- Exact diagnostic lab number unknown due to project time limit
- Clinic size limited generalization for bigger organization

Implications for Practice

- PDSA model is effective in driving practice change
- Providers need to assess patients' barriers
- Focused education on benefits of HCV screening and treatment (staff, patient, and family)
- Encourage F/U appointments

Conclusions

- EBP guidelines can assist providers to effectively screen and treat patients
- Opportunity to educate and raise HCV awareness, reduce disease transmission
- New standardized HCV protocol approved, adopted for the clinic, ongoing evaluation of its effectiveness
- Currently used by staff and providers to improve HCV care, treatment outcomes, and enhance patients' quality of life

References upon request gsubedi@csu.fullerton.edu